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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY TO ASSESS THE
PREVELENC OF TREATMENT RELATED ANEMIA IN
PATIENTS WITH HEPATITIS C****¹Dr. Saba Aziz, ²Dr Zara Arshad, ³Dr Anum Rizwan**¹Demonstrator, Poonch Medical College Rawlakot²WMO, DHQ Hospital South City Okara³WMO, BHU Lalapindi**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate the prevalence of treatment-related anemia in chronic hepatitis C patients receiving ribavirin and pegylated interferon alpha in combination therapy.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in the department of medicine, Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi from June 2019 to November 2019. A total of 50 subjects with hepatitis C in chronic stage were nominated for interferon-alpha and ribavirin at standard doses for 24 weeks.

Results: During the study period, the majority of the patients were between 41 and 50 years of age, ie 32% (n = 16), and the mean and standard deviation were 38.33 + 4.60, and 38% (n =19) were male and 62% (n = 31) were female. The treatment given for 2 weeks, the incidence of treatment-induced anemia was 24% (n = 12) and they were anemic.

Conclusion: The frequency of treatment-related anemia in chronic hepatitis C patients treated with ribavirin and pegylated interferon alpha in the 2nd week of treatment suggests significant anemia.

Key words: Anemia, treatment, hepatitis C.

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INTRODUCTION:

3-10% of the Pakistan population have hepatitis C virus in chronic stage, and the genotype 3 is the most common subtype in our populations. For hepatitis C, the treatment recommended is pegylated interferon alpha and Ribavirin for 24 or 48 weeks. Approximately 65% of the patients developed influenza-like symptoms, sleep disorders, loss of appetite, depression, continuous fever, anemia, thrombocytopenia, neutropenia and rash. Ribavirin also causes dose-dependent reversible hemolytic anemia, which results in an average decrease of 3.7 g / dl of hemoglobin (Hb) within 4 weeks with the myelo-suppressive effects of interferon. This anemia <10 / dl occurred in 20.5% of patients at 14 days after treatment begin. Before the start of treatment, Hb (hemoglobin) levels were higher than 12 g / dl, and who had to stop treatment due to severe anemia were taking Ribavirin in 14%. The patients aged 60 years and older discontinuation was more common. In univariate analysis, ribavirin dose reduction significantly affected ribavirin-induced hemolytic anemia. In patients with HCC managed with IFN alpha, interferon alpha (IFN) and Ribavirin (IFN + RIB) anemia were observed in 37.5% and 56.6%, respectively. In multivariate analysis, patients with hemoglobin and renal insufficiency before treatment at an age of 14 g / dl and at the age of 55 years may have increased the risk of ribavirin-induced anemia. In a standard interferon regimen and high doses of ribavirin (1000-1200 mg / d), 54% of patients had a reduction of more than 3 g / dl in hemoglobin at some point during 48 weeks of treatment. The mean reduction in HB is two to three g / dl in the first 4 weeks of treatment, for many patients this response is influenced by the co-suppression of the interferon associated bone marrow. 8-9% of patients approximately treated with combined therapy had a decrease in hemoglobin levels to less than 10 g / dL, 13-23% of patients had interferon alpha/ or ribavirin alpha. According to the study conducted by Natinall, Hemoglobin (Hb) had a mean decrease of 0.87 d / dl at 3 months and antiviral therapy at 2 g / dl for 6 months. 10% of the patients developed anemia, 6 months after the antiviral treatment, 2 g / dl and 10% anemia. Patients developed anemia after 6 months of antiviral treatment. In Pakistan, anemia-induced therapy (Hb months11g / dl) was found in 7% of cases in three months. Hemoglobin may

increase the risk of treatment-related anemia in patients with previous 12 g / dl and those aged 55 and over and with renal impairment. According to available evidence, treatment-related anemia is also prominent and frequent during treatment. In this study, we plan to find the frequency of anemia in 2 weeks. If this frequency seems to be higher, we may recommend early management steps to be taken.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive cross-sectional survey was held in the Medical Unit II of Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi for One year duration from September 2017 to September 2018. Fifty (50) patients were selected for the study. The risk of treatment and aim were explained to the patients, and informed consent in written state was taken. If the patient meets the inclusion criteria when taken in Medicine OPD, the treatment was initiated (pegylated interferon alpha 2b plus 1.5 mg / kg once a week) and hemoglobin levels were evaluated at the end of the first week and finally at the second week. If anemia is detected at any time during the treatment, compassionate and appropriate additional actions will be taken. The patients were treated according to the standard protocol. These patients were observed very closely with frequent follow-ups in OPD. Hemoglobin was done in the hospital lab. All this information was collected with performa. Using version 14.0 of SPSS data was analyzed. Quantitative variables of the study were measured as mean $\pm$ standard deviation and age, qualitative variables were measured as sex and frequency of anemia caused by treatment

RESULTS:

In order to evaluate the prevalence of treatment related anemia in patients with hepatitis C in chronic stage who received ribavirin and pegylated interferon alpha combination therapy, a total of 50 patients were selected for the analysis. The age distribution of the patients was between 20-30 years of age and 24% (n = 12) of the patients, 30% (n = 15) between 31-40 years of age, 32% (n = 16). While between 41 and 50 years of age, only 14% (n = 7), between 51 and 55 years of age, had a mean and standard deviation of 38.33 $\pm$ 4.60 (Table 1).

Age (yrs)	n	%
20-30	12	24
31-40	15	30
41-50	16	32
51-55	07	14
Total	50	100
Mean and SD	38.33-4.60	

Table 2 shows that 38% (n = 19) of the male patients and 62% (n = 31) were female.

Gender	n	%
Male	19	38
Female	31	62
Total	50	100

In the second week of treatment, the incidence of anemia caused by treatment was 3% (n = 12), while it was calculated in Table 3, 76% (n = 38) was not anemic (Table 3).

Anemia	n	%
Yes	12	24
No	38	76
Total	50	100

DISCUSSION:

Currently, 130-170 million people worldwide are infected with hepatitis C virus (HCV). More than 70% of HCV infections become chronic and if untreated, cirrhosis and liver transplantation require hepatocellular carcinoma. The ability to improve treatment response rates makes ribavirin necessary for the treatment of HCV infection. To maximize the benefit of ribavirin patients, the limiting side effect of treatment with antiviral activity requires the right balance of hemolytic anemia. In Pakistan, treatment related anemia (Hb an11 g / dl) was found in 7% of cases in three months. It was aimed to determine the frequency of anemia in the second week of treatment. If this frequency seems to be greater, it is rationalized that we can recommend early management measures to control. In our study, in contrast to a study by Nomura H, we found that 24% of the study colleagues found 2% reduction in 24% of patients with anemia to identify factors contributing to anemia caused by cancer patients. / dL hemoglobin The concentrations in patients with anemia were observed at week 2 after the start of treatment. It was observed that hemoglobin concentration was significantly lower in patients with > 2 or 2 g / dl decrease at 2 weeks (P <0.01). Oze T and its staff conducted a study in Japan to study the factors associated with the progression of ribavirin-induced hemolytic anemia in patients with chronic hepatitis C treated with combination therapy with interferon and ribavirin, and Hb was greater than 12 g / dl prior to treatment, 68 patients (14% had to stop treatment with ribavirin due to severe anemia. Patients with a "2 to 2" positive group (Hb), decreased to over 2 g / dl) with the lowest CL / F (apparent clearance) were more frequent than patients under 60 years of age due to severe anemia Interruption, 60 years and older (%) 21 to 9%, P <0.001). Among patients aged 60 years and older, only the "2 x 2" standard was significantly associated with discontinuation of ribavirin due to severe anemia in a multivariate analysis (rate ratio, 4.18, P <0.001). The results of this study are also consistent with the previous study because the range of our subjects was only up to 55 years, but

on the other hand, a limitation was observed due to the study. The reason why anemia is not classified by age in our study is due to a 30.4% of patients in the age group that is > 40 years of age and due to a weak socioeconomic class in our country. However, the results of this study and other studies suggest that anemia in 2 weeks may be the cause of discontinuation of the treatment and other important parameters suggest that treatment of the elderly may cause anemia in patients with hepatitis, combined therapy field Chronic C Alpha pegylated interferon and ribavirin. In addition, it may help to take early management measures to control anemia (after the second week) caused by early-identified treatment.

CONCLUSION:

The frequency of treatment-related anemia in patients with chronic hepatitis C treated with pegylated interferon alpha and ribavirin or in combination in the second week of treatment reveals marked anemia.

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